

Conditional Seasonal Markov-Switching Autoregressive Model to Simulate Extreme Events: Application to River Flow

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Abstract

Extreme events have the potential to significantly impact transportation infrastructure performance. For example, in the case of bridges, climate change impacts the river discharge, hence scouring patterns, which in turn, affects the bridge foundation stability. Therefore, extreme events (river flow) prediction is mandatory in bridge reliability analysis. This paper approaches this river flow prediction problem by developing a Markov-Switching Autoregressive model coupled with a conditional hidden seasonal Markov component. In addition, the proposed model is also combined with the deep machine learning neural networks method to forecast river flow from a dataset or from simulations. The proposed method is illustrated by using realistic data: historic river flow values of the Thames River. The results indicate that the proposed model well represented the extreme events within the dataset. In terms of river flow forecasting, the results indicate that the forecasts improve when the training period changes from 20 years to 40 years.

Keywords: Seasonal Markov-Switching Autoregressive model; Conditional hidden seasonal Markov process; River flow forecasting; Extreme events; Recurrent Neural Networks.

Software availability: data and developed code in R language are available in the public repository: https://github.com/ebastidasarteaga/SMSAR_model

Notation and Acronyms:

AR:	Autoregressive process.
ARIMA:	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average.
c :	Constant term of the Autoregressive process.
E :	Severe values limit.
Ev_t :	Months of interest effect value.
HSM :	Conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component.
I and J :	Markovian regimes states.
k :	Markovian state.
M :	Switching regimes number.
MES_y :	Monthly effect based on the yearly seasonality.
ML:	Machine learning.
Moi_t :	Months of interest increase rate.
MS:	Markov-Switching.
MSAR:	Markov-Switching Autoregressive.
NHMSAR:	(Non)- Homogeneous Markov-Switching Autoregressive.
NN:	Deep machine learning Neural Networks forecasting method.

$n_{t_{Moi}}$:	Number of months of interest.
p :	Autoregressive order.
Q :	Upper quartile of the dataset.
S_m :	Seasonal transition probability matrix.
SMSAR:	Seasonal Markov-Switching Autoregressive.
S_t :	Hidden Markov chain.
S_y :	Yearly seasonality.
S_{yR} :	Yearly seasonality remainder.
t :	Months of the year.
t_{Moi} :	Months of interest.
t_y :	Yearly time series.
WN :	White Noise.
X_t :	Time state.
Y_t :	Monthly time series state.
Z :	Lower quartile of the dataset.
φ :	Autoregressive model parameter.
Ψ :	Current state of the probability transition matrix.
ε_t :	Errors.
μ :	Mean value.
ε_t :	Random white noise.
σ :	Standard deviation.
Ω :	Transition state of the probability transition matrix.
σ^2 :	Variance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The lifetime of infrastructure assets depends on a variety of aspects, which include construction materials, the evolution of the demand, changes in the surrounding environment, as well as design assumptions, maintenance, and operation policies. All physical systems change and suffer a loss in capacity through time due to progressive deterioration (corrosion, fatigue, creep, etc.) [1–3] or shock-based deterioration (extreme events) [4]. This decrease in capacity yields an increase in the likelihood of failure and therefore, regular inspections and maintenance are essential to ensure adherence to the necessary safety standards [5–7]. In the case of bridges crossing rivers, scouring is a common problem that threatens the structure’s integrity. It is caused mainly by extreme flood events that remove sediments of riverbed materials around the bridge foundations. Local scour is one of the main reasons for the loss of structural capacity and failures of bridges due to high river discharge values [8–10]. As an example, scouring is responsible for 60 percent of bridge failures in the United States, resulting in an annual maintenance cost of \$30 million [11].

Extreme weather events such as droughts and floods are expected to increase in frequency and intensity in some places due to climate change, which in turn will impact the infrastructure in several ways [12]. In the case of bridges crossing rivers, climate change may have a direct impact on the river discharge and, consequently, may modify the bridge scouring patterns since precipitation patterns could become more volatile and unpredictable, causing floods. Accordingly, forecasting river flow is essential for identifying potential problems such as droughts or floods, formulating mitigation plans, and increasing resilience. In addition, this is also important to make informed decisions about water allocation and management. Forecasting river flows is mostly based on climate models and historical time series forecasting methods. Climate models are used to construct Representative Concentration Pathways scenarios [13,14]; however, their results are highly uncertain due to climate models' variability, forcing factors, aerosols, jet stream impact, resolution, etc. On the other hand, time series forecasting methods may be a preferable choice since they are based on actual data observed directly from the system.

Hydrological time series models make predictions based on historical data, from which it is possible to extract statistical information and associated seasonal and cyclic patterns [15–17]. For example, a quantum leap within the long-term dependence occurred by considering the fractionally integrated process within the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, this is achieved by inserting the long-term dependence into the Box & Jenkins framework, and the resulting model is the Autoregressive Fractional Integrated Moving Average (ARFIMA) model. This model can simulate the river flow, as it captures the long-term memory and the non-stationary nature of the system. Nevertheless, even with seasonal effects, this model shows inaccurate hydrological forecasts due to the conservation of the mean value in the analysis. For example, in the case study of the Tisza River [18], the ARFIMA model with seasonal effects failed to simulate the river flow hydrological fact, i.e., high river flow values for a short time interval are followed by low river flow values for a long time interval.

The regime-switching technique can be used to improve the model performance to simulate the previously mentioned river flow hydrological fact, this is achieved by embedding latent regimes equivalent to wet and dry periods [19–21]. Consequently, regime-switching models are a preferable choice within the framework of hydrological time series analysis. The regime-switching process improves the concept of stochastic processes within the context of time series analysis by using the hidden Markov process [22]; this process is a type of probabilistic model used to describe a sequence of events or observations where the state is not directly visible, but the output, dependent on the state,

is visible, i.e., changes in mean and variance. The Markov-Switching (MS) process was proposed to capture the discrete changes as a result of the volatility behavior detected in economic applications [23].

The Markov-Switching Autoregressive (MSAR) model is an improvement to the Markov-Switching (MS) process, providing a more comprehensive method for identifying structural breaks in the time series dynamics by embedding an autoregressive component. This helps to describe the time evolution of the series more accurately, in which the switching between these processes is regulated by a hidden Markov chain. Accordingly, the MSAR model was first approached within the context of statistical climate analysis in 2007, as climatic conditions depend on past patterns [24], in which the variations within the MSAR model were associated with periodic severe volatility [25]. Further investigations assured the ability of the MSAR model to accurately represent climatic changes [26,27]. In addition, the significance of the regime-switching process arose in modeling the seasonal accumulation of the river flow hydrological fact, i.e., high river flow values for a short time interval are followed by low river flow values for a long time interval [28]. However, the main limitation within the latest regime-switching models when simulating a hydrological time series dataset is the low quality of the simulations over a long period (hundreds of years), especially its ability to simulate extreme events/severe values. In other words, the Markov-Switching approach has been investigated in neither simulating a long time series dataset nor detecting extreme events.

Recently, Machine Learning (ML) methods have been applied within the context of hydrological time-series predictions with great success due to their ability to make predictions, in which the performance of ML methods has surpassed traditional mathematical models by effectively addressing complex regression mathematical problems [29]. The artificial intelligence Neural Network (NN) system is composed of interconnected neurons, which process and transmit information from the historical dataset to solve complex problems. The NN systems, i.e., Recurrent, Random forest, Convolutional, and Multiple perception, have shown success within the context of hydrological time series predictions [30,31]. The integration of a regime-switching process into the Recurrent NN system has been shown to improve the precision of the forecasts, as the regime-switching process helps the NN system to better recognize and respond to changes in the data [32]. In addition, the length of the historical patterns fed into the model seems to impact the accuracy of the forecasts and should be further investigated [33,34].

The objective of this paper is to propose a model based on a Markov-Switching (MS) process to simulate severe river flow values, i.e., extreme events for a long dataset since the Markov-Switching

approach has been investigated in neither simulating a long time series dataset nor detecting extreme events. In addition, the paper investigates the impact of the training period on the forecasts generated by the Recurrent NN system, and whether forecasting a simulation can be as effective as an actual forecasted dataset, given that, the period of the training process has not been previously investigated in river flow forecasting. In this paper, we first propose a Seasonal Markov-Switching Autoregressive (SMSAR) model to simulate severe river flow values. The SMSAR model is initiated as MSAR model and is then coupled with a conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov (HSM) component to enhance its performance. Afterward, the SMSAR simulation is then integrated with the deep machine learning Neural Networks (NN) method, i.e., Recurrent NN system to evaluate the SMSAR model's ability to forecast time series. All methodological developments are illustrated with the hydrological time-series analysis of the Thames River, and the results are compared with those of the MSAR model.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2.1 provides an overview of the numerical phases considered for simulating the SMSAR model, severe values, and forecasting; these numerical phases are also illustrated by a pseudo code algorithm in Appendix. 1. Section 2.2 provides an in-depth illustration of the SMSAR model. Section 2.3 sets out the threshold for determining severe values. Section 3.1 describes the case study that will be analyzed and discussed in Section 3.2 to assess the quality of the proposed SMSAR model and its ability to detect severe values. Section 3.3 investigates using the Recurrent Neural Networks method for prediction purposes. In addition, this section also investigates the training period's impact on pattern recognition.

2. METHODS

2.1. General description

This paper presents the SMSAR model to simulate severe river flow values, i.e., extreme flood events, and to predict potential flooding by integrating the deep machine learning NN method. This is of utmost importance since the consequences of flooding can be devastating, leading to physical damage to infrastructure, and loss of life. Moreover, it helps policymakers to develop effective water management strategies, flood control measures, and mitigation plans. The methodology consists of five main phases, i.e., Dataset preparation, model identification, model fitting, extreme events detection, and forecasting the simulations using Recurrent Neural Network (NN) system. The input of the time series analysis is the historical river flow values of the Thames River. These phases are demonstrated in Appendix. 1 as follows:

In the first phase of this process, the time series dataset is presented with a monthly frequency and tested for non-stationary behavior. This is performed to determine whether the dataset's mean and variance change over time. However, the stationary behavior of the time series will not be accurately computed when the time series has long-term behavior. Subsequently, the long-term behavior is examined in the model identification phase, and the type of the model is specified. In this case of long-term behavior, a structural break test is performed to indicate whether a Markov-Switching Autoregressive model is suitable for simulating the dataset.

In the third phase, two regimes within the Markov-Switching process are presented to describe the latent regimes equivalent to wet and dry periods. In addition, the autoregressive order is estimated using the Akaike Info Criterion (AIC) method. Additionally, the simulation is approached with a conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component, this component consists of state and condition phases. The state phase defines the months of interest and provides their effect value. In parallel, the condition phase determines the years of seasonality and allocates the months of interest effect value to the years of seasonality.

The fourth phase detects the extreme events based on the interquartile range of the monthly dataset and considers the months of interest to discriminate the limit of the severe values. Finally, the forecasting phase uses the NN system, i.e., Recurrent NN to provide predictions. This forecasting method comprises the effect of monthly seasonality.

2.2. SMSAR Model

The proposed Seasonal Markov-Switching Autoregressive (SMSAR) model is a discrete-time process based on three components that will be detailed below, i.e., Hidden Seasonal Markov process (HSM), Markov-Switching process (MS), and Autoregressive process (AR). The analysis of the MSAR model components is carried out by the NHMSAR package in R Statistical Software with the addition of the proposed Hidden Seasonal Markov component [35].

The SMSAR model dynamics are based on the statistical information of the historical dataset, in which the dynamics of the model are the result of the autoregressive process. Furthermore, the dynamics variation is based on the Markov-Switching process which is significant in the simulation of consecutive events since each regime includes the characteristics of a specific time domain. In a sense, two regimes are used to present the behavior of high and low river flow values. In addition, the proposed Hidden Seasonal Markov component aims to enhance the ability of the MSAR model to

simulate extreme values by computing the months of interest and the years of seasonality, in which the months of interest effect value will be applied at those time states, i.e., years of seasonality.

2.2.1. Autoregressive component

The Autoregressive process is based on the assumption that the current values of a time series are dependent on past values to capture the dynamics of the process over time. This is controlled by the parameters of the process to represent the decomposed components of the past values, i.e., level, trend, pattern, and random noise, in which the autoregressive order is the measure of the number of past values taken into account to estimate the current value. The autoregressive process of order p is symbolized as $AR(p)$ at time t , writes:

$$X_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i X_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t; \varepsilon_t \sim WN(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2) \quad (1)$$

where X_t is the current time state, φ is a parameter of the model, c is the constant term of the process, ε_t is a random white noise WN and σ_ε^2 is the variance of the random white noise.

2.2.2. Markov switching component

The Markov switching process captures the changes in the dynamics of a time series over time. In a sense, it is used to identify different regimes in the data, and to estimate the transition probabilities between these regimes. The Markov-switching process is based on the regime's time-varying transition probability matrix, this process relies on the current state of Markov chain regimes. The transition probability state of the hidden Markov chain writes:

$$P(\mathcal{S}_t = I | \mathcal{S}_{t-1} = J) = P(I|J); \mathcal{S}_t \in \{1, \dots, M\} \quad (2)$$

where M is the number of regimes, \mathcal{S}_t is the Hidden Markov chain state space, I and $J \in \mathcal{S}_t$ and represent the Markovian regimes.

The MSAR model is a discrete-time process with two components $\{X_t, \mathcal{S}_t\}$, in this particular application, $\{X_t\}$ denotes the evolution of the monthly river flow discharge and $\mathcal{S}_t \in \{\text{Regime 1, Regime 2}\}$ represents the latent two regime states of low and high river flow values, respectively, as presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Transition probability diagram.

The MSAR model general formula represented in Eq. (3) explicates the stochastic relationship of the regimes switching Markovian chain represented in Eq. (2) with the autoregressive component represented in Eq. (1). In this application, the MSAR model represented in Eq. (4) presents the dynamics of a time series with an autoregressive model of order two, in which the switching between the two regimes of low and high river flow is controlled by a hidden Markov chain, writes:

$$Y_t | Y_{t-1} = \sum_{k=1}^M P(\mathcal{S}_t) \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_{i|k} Y_{t-i} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$(Y_t | Y_{t-1} | \mathcal{S}_t): \begin{cases} Y_t = c_1 + \varphi_1^1 X_{t-1} + \varphi_2^1 X_{t-2} + \varepsilon_t, & \text{when } \mathcal{S}_t = 1 \\ Y_t = c_2 + \varphi_1^2 X_{t-1} + \varphi_2^2 X_{t-2} + \varepsilon_t, & \text{when } \mathcal{S}_t = 2 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where Y_t is the monthly time series state, k is a Markovian regime state $\varepsilon \in \mathcal{S}_t$, φ_i^M represents the autoregressive coefficient of order i for regime M , and c_M is the constant term of the process for regime M .

2.2.3. Conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component

The conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component consists of state and condition phases. The state phase detects the months of interest and provides the months of interest effect. Then, the condition phase defines the years of seasonality and allocates the months of interest effect to the years of seasonality. This component is proposed to simulate severe values, i.e., high river flow values within the SMSAR model.

The state phase considers the positive variance percentage ratio of the months in Eq. (5) the indicator of determining the months of interest. In this way, the actual results of the months of interest exceed the expected result based on the entire months, indicating a sign of growth. In addition, the state phase computes the effect value of the months of interest in Eq. (6) based on the adjusted expected mean of the months of interest accordingly to the variance percentage increase value. This is carried out to

compute and relate the mean value of the months of interest to the spread of the data between different monthly distributions. The state phase writes:

$$Moi_t = \left[\frac{\mu(\sum_{t_y=1}^n \sigma^2(t))}{\mu(\sum_{t_y=1}^n (\sum_{t=1}^{12} \sigma^2(t)))} \times 100 \right] - 100 > 0; (t | t_y) \in \{1, \dots, 12\} \quad (5)$$

$$Ev_t = \mu(\sum_{t_y=1}^n t_{Moi}) \times \left[100 - \frac{(Moi_t | t_{Moi})}{100} \right]; t_y \in \{1, \dots, n\} \quad (6)$$

where Moi_t is the months of interest increase rate, t are the months of the year, σ^2 is the variance, t_y is the yearly time series, Ev_t is the months of interest effect value and t_{Moi} are the months of interest based on the months of interest increase rate.

The condition phase determines the years of seasonality and allocates the months of interest to the years of seasonality based on their variability. First, the condition phase determines the years of seasonality in Eq. (7) based on the yearly variance by stating that, when the variance of the data in a single year exceeds the average, then that year is considered a year of seasonality. This is an indication that the year has experienced extreme values, and the monthly data distribution is more spread.

$$S_y = \sigma^2(t_y) > \mu \sum_{t_y=1}^n \sigma^2(t_y) \quad (7)$$

where S_y are the years of seasonality.

The condition phase then distributes the months of interest across the years of seasonality based on the mean value of the yearly variability of the dataset as follows: The overall variability for each year of seasonality in Eq. (8) is utilized to measure the degree to which each year of seasonality differs from the average of all years which is used to identify changes in seasonal patterns over time, then by relating the overall variability for a given year of seasonality to the average value for the months of interest over the years in Eq. (9), it is possible to allocate the overall variability for a given year of seasonality to the months of interest, allowing for potential seasonal trends to be implemented.

$$S_{yR} = \sigma^2(t_y | S_y) - \mu \sum_{t_y=1}^n \sigma^2(t_y) \quad (8)$$

$$MES_y = \min \left\{ S_{yR} \mid \mu \left(\sum_{t_y=1}^n \sigma^2(t_{Moi}) \right) \right\} \quad (9)$$

where S_{yR} is the overall variability for each year of seasonality, and MES_y is the monthly effect based on the years of seasonality.

The conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component consists of state and condition phases, this component allocates the months of interest effect value from the state phase in Eq. (6) to the time series based on the monthly effect of the years of seasonality from the condition phase in Eq. (9). This component is a process that allows the SMSAR model to accurately capture the seasonal yearly fluctuations in the time series and allocate the effect value accordingly, it writes:

$$HSM = (Ev_t | MES_y) \quad (10)$$

where HSM is the conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component value.

The SMSAR model represented in Eq. (11) is an improvement of the MSAR model in Eq. (3) due to the integration of the conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component from Eq. (10). Subsequently, the simulation is enhanced by considering an additional value based on the effect values of the months of interest in Eq. (6) and allocates this value to the time series with respect to the years of seasonality in Eq. (9), allowing for potential seasonal trends to be implemented. This method is proposed to simulate severe values, i.e., high river flow values, writes:

$$Y_t | Y_{t-1} = \sum_{k=1}^M P(S_t) \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_{i|k} Y_{t-i} \right) + (HSM | (S_m)) \quad (11)$$

$$S_m = \begin{bmatrix} t_{Moi}^{\langle \Psi, \Omega \rangle} & \dots & t_{Moi}^{\langle \Psi, \Omega \rangle} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ t_{Moi}^{\langle \Psi, \Omega \rangle} & \dots & t_{Moi}^{\langle \Psi, \Omega \rangle} \end{bmatrix}; \quad (t_{Moi}^{\langle \Psi, \Omega \rangle} | t) \in \{1, \dots, 12\} \quad (12)$$

where S_m is the seasonal transition probability matrix that is estimated as the probabilistic transition between the months of interest effect value of the HSM states, Ψ represents the current state, and Ω represents the transition state within the months of interest. In this particular application, the seasonal transition probability matrix, writes:

$$S_m = \begin{bmatrix} t_{Moi}^{\langle 1,1 \rangle} & t_{Moi}^{\langle 1,2 \rangle} & t_{Moi}^{\langle 1,12 \rangle} \\ t_{Moi}^{\langle 2,1 \rangle} & t_{Moi}^{\langle 2,2 \rangle} & t_{Moi}^{\langle 2,12 \rangle} \\ t_{Moi}^{\langle 12,1 \rangle} & t_{Moi}^{\langle 12,2 \rangle} & t_{Moi}^{\langle 12,12 \rangle} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

2.3. Severe values

The severe values detection method is proposed to detect the outliers of the monthly distributed dataset over their historical period. The method is based on the interquartile range of the monthly dataset [36] and considers the months of interest to discriminate the limit of the severe values, it writes:

$$E = \frac{\sum_i^{t_{Moi}} [Q_i + 1.5[Q_i - Z_i]]}{n_{t_{Moi}}} \quad (14)$$

where E is the limit to detect severe values, Q_i is the upper quartile of the dataset, Z_i is the lower quartile of the dataset, and $n_{t_{Moi}}$ is the number of months of interest counted from the t_{Moi} in Eq. (6).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section estimates the accuracy of the proposed SMSAR model, its ability to simulate extreme events, and forecast river flow. All results will be compared with those provided by the MSAR model.

3.1. Dataset Description

Thames River is considered to illustrate the proposed model within the framework of extreme events detection. The Thames is considered a vital testbed since it is the longest river in England and has one of the longest flow records associated with any United Kingdom flow gauging station from 1883 till 2020. Several studies on flood risk management indicated that the Thames is a flood-prone river and is considered a vital testbed [37–40]. The historical dataset of daily river flow measurements from Windsor and Teddington stations was extracted from the United Kingdom national river flow archive [41].

In Fig. 2, the historical monthly dataset and yearly variance of the Thames River demonstrate the dynamic nature and fluctuations of the river's flow values. The fluctuations within the monthly river flow values and yearly variance values ensure that the Thames is a vital testbed for extreme events research and analysis.

Fig. 2. Dataset description. (a) Monthly dataset, (b) Yearly variance.

3.2. Data Processing

This section aims to assess the quality of the proposed SMSAR model and its ability to detect severe values, i.e., maximum river flow values. The analysis sections are as follows: Statistical analysis, Probability distribution, Accuracy analysis, and Extreme events analysis.

3.2.1. Statistical analysis

This section describes the relation between the simulations and the dataset. In addition, inhere we analyze the relative frequency and the intensity of upcrossings of predefined intervals of the models, this analysis displays the number of times a simulation passes upwards or downwards through an interval. Since it is important to correctly interpret the statistical analysis, the results of the simulations are then compared with those of the dataset to discuss their variations and assess their quality.

In Fig. 3, the outputs of the simulations (SMSAR and MSAR) and the dataset values are presented. In addition, deterministic values are presented to illustrate the proportion of variance, i.e., the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the strength of the linear association, i.e., Pearson correlation coefficient (R). It is observed that the SMSAR model provides a better fit to the dataset. This is evidenced by the superior results of the deterministic values of the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Pearson correlation coefficient (R). In a sense, the SMSAR model less deviates from the dataset and presents a better linear relation with the dataset.

In Fig. 4, the residuals are fitted to their simulations distribution, this aims to introduce the variations within the range limit values of the simulations and compare them to the range limit of the dataset, i.e., maximum value. The range limit value of the dataset is 391 m³/sec, this value is surpassed in one

state by the SMSAR model with a value of $426 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. On the other hand, the MSAR model has a lower range limit in comparison to the dataset with a range limit value of $254 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$.

The results demonstrate that, first, the river flow variations are better presented by the SMSAR model. Second, low and high river flow values are well presented by the embedded 2 regime-switching within the MSAR and SMSAR models which is explained by the positive Pearson correlation coefficient value. It is interesting to note that, the SMSAR model improves this value.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the river flow dataset with the SMSAR and MSAR simulations.

Fig. 4. Analysis of the residuals for each model.

In line with the statistical analysis, the relative frequency, and the intensity of upcrossings illustrate the occurrence of specific events, i.e., the percentage of occurrence, and the shifting between time series levels, respectively. It is important to note that the following findings are based on an interval sequential distribution of $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. In a sense, the simulations are based on a sequential distribution of the river flow starting from 0 to the maximum river flow value with a range value of $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ for each increment.

In Fig. 5, the observed relative frequency distribution emphasizes that when exceeding $170 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$, superior results are achieved by the SMSAR model. Moreover, the SMSAR model seems to improve the findings when exceeding $250 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ since the MSAR model did not present values above this limit as shown in Fig. 4. However, both models show larger differences when they are below $70 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$.

The results demonstrate two statements. First, two regimes-switching within the MSAR model were not efficient to explain extremely low and high values. Second, this analysis found evidence that the SMSAR model suffers from the same limitations associated with the MSAR model for low values. However, the SMSAR model seems to improve findings for high values since the SMSAR model improves the pre-initiated MSAR simulation by embedding the conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component in Eq. (10) that allocates the months of interest effect value to the time series based on the monthly effect of the years of seasonality.

Fig. 5. Statistical distribution study.

In Fig. 6, the statistical intensity study indicates that both models underestimate the shifting behavior when below $40 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. However, superior results are seen for the SMSAR model above $150 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. The results of the study support the notion that the Hidden Seasonal Markov component within the SMSAR model reallocates the statistical properties of the pre-initiated MSAR simulation.

Fig. 6. Statistical intensity study. (a) The number of upcrossings, (b) Difference in the number of upcrossings.

3.2.2. Probability distribution

This section presents the probability distribution and parametric classifications of the distribution, i.e., spread and shape. The results of the simulations are compared with the values obtained from the dataset to discuss their variations and assess their quality in terms of a probability distribution.

In Fig. 7, the non-parametric kernel probability distribution is used to represent the statistical classification, i.e., asymmetry and tail distribution of the river flow. The results indicate that the dataset, SMSAR, and MSAR models are classified by shape distribution as asymmetrical right-skewed distributions with values of 1.59, 1.68, and 1.06, respectively. In a sense, the dataset and the SMSAR model values of the distributions are concentrated around low values and the right tail presents a low percentage of occurrence for higher values. However, the MSAR model distribution is classified by shape as a slightly asymmetrical right-skewed distribution with no outliers or extreme values since the skew value is nearly equal to 1.

Fig. 7. Probabilistic analysis.

A graphical analysis (Q-Q plot) is carried out between the probability distributions by plotting their quantiles against the theoretical quantile, i.e., normal distribution. The applicability of this analysis is to test whether the distributions are normally distributed.

In Fig. 8, it is noted that the samples' quantiles do not align with the theoretical quantiles. This indicates that the distributions are not normally distributed. In addition, the shape of distributions is asymmetrical right-skewed since the upper end of the Q-Q plot deviates from the linear trend. The lower end of the Q-Q plot is horizontal, which appears to be the case of repetitive values and presents a high concentration around lower values within the distributions. The results also indicate that the SMSAR model improves the representation of the distribution with respect to the dataset in comparison to the MSAR model.

Fig. 8. Q-Q plot.

3.2.3. Accuracy analysis

This section evaluates the ability of the models to fit the dataset by comparing the results of their residuals and error indicators. In addition, this section demonstrates whether there is missing statistical information that should be accounted for in the models since the Markov-Switching regime's approach suffers from the limitation that volatile changes in the time series neglect the time series assumption of independent errors.

In Fig. 9, the MSAR model residuals are widely distributed, reaching a value of $-258 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. On the other hand, the SMSAR model residuals are less scattered, with a variance that is 57.11 % of the MSAR model's.

Fig. 9. Models' residuals distribution.

The distribution of the residuals is then analyzed by presenting their relative frequency to demonstrate to which degree the residuals are distributed. The relative frequency is based on an interval sequential distribution of $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. In a sense, the simulations are based on a sequential distribution of the river flow starting from 0 to the maximum river flow value with a range value of $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ for each increment.

In Fig. 10, the distributions of the residuals indicate that slightly superior frequencies are achieved with the SMSAR model in comparison to the MSAR model within the distribution range between $0 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ to $40 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. Moreover, superior lower frequencies for the SMSAR model are observed within the distribution below $-50 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$.

This is evidence for the underestimation considered within the MSAR model due to the model's two regimes dynamic. However, this is improved by considering the Hidden Seasonal Markov component within the SMSAR model. Together, the present results of the models' residuals distribution and histogram confirm that the SMSAR model seems to provide a better fit to the dataset because of the fewer deviations.

Fig. 10. Models' residuals histogram. (a) Negative residuals histogram, (b) Positive residuals histogram.

It is important to accurately interpret the residuals to assess the accuracy of the models compared to the dataset, therefore, in Table 1, the residuals are presented in terms of descriptive values to provide deterministic meaning. The error indicators for the SMSAR model present an increase in precision.

Table 1. Error indicators.

Model	RMSE**	MAE***	MAPE****	SME*****
SMSAR	33.28	26.65	89.99	0.75
MSAR	41.30	30.73	91.84	1.00

* Mean error. (m³/sec)

** Square root of the average square errors. (m³/sec)

*** Mean absolute error. (m³/sec)

**** Mean absolute percentage error. (%)

***** Standard mean error. (m³/sec)

The autocorrelation of the residuals is computed to indicate whether there is still missing statistical information that should be accounted for within the SMSAR model. This aspect is important since the model includes a Markov-Switching process which may arise autocorrelation in the residuals, which in turn violates the assumption of independent errors. In a sense, exceeding the confidence interval indicates missing statistical information that should be considered in the model.

In Fig. 11, it is noted that the autocorrelation of the SMSAR model residuals is lower than that obtained from the MSAR model. However, there is some missing statistical information not considered by the SMSAR model for non-seasonal lags. Indeed, non-seasonal lags are the lags that exclude the seasonal monthly lags, i.e., 12, and 24.

The results demonstrate that the proposed conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component within the SMSAR model significantly improves the results for seasonal lags, which implies that an improvement

in the seasonal patterns is associated with the SMSAR model. Also, the SMSAR model still slightly suffers from the same limitations associated with the MSAR model analysis for the non-seasonal lags, i.e., errors are not completely random, but instead are following a pattern. Despite that, the SMSAR model also improves the results for the non-seasonal lags.

Fig. 11. Autocorrelation function (ACF) of the residuals.

3.2.4. Extreme events analysis

One major limitation of recent studies in time series analysis is the ability to simulate extreme values. In this section, the ability of the SMSAR and MSAR models to simulate extreme events is tested.

The proposed extreme events limit is considered based on the interquartile range of the pre-determined months of interest of the monthly distributed dataset; this method is mentioned in Eq. (14) (See section 2.3). Subsequently, the river flow value of $260 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ is considered to be the limit of extreme events.

In Fig. 12, the dataset and the SMSAR model present 19 and 15 extreme events, respectively. On the other hand, the MSAR model failed to simulate any extreme event. It is important to mention that despite the impressive performance achieved by the SMSAR model within the framework of extreme events detection, the SMSAR model underestimated five extreme events on 11/1894, 12/1910, 12/1929, 03/1947, and 02/1990, and overestimated one extreme event on 02/1915. The results ensure that the SMSAR model is capable of simulating extreme events since the SMSAR model detected 15 extreme events out of 19 extreme events in a monthly time series of length 1656 starting from 1883 to 2022.

Fig. 12. Extreme events detection.

In Fig. 13, the difference in extreme events values with respect to the dataset shows that the deviations of the SMSAR model are concentrated within the range of $-10 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ to $20 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$ with a mean absolute error value of $30 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$.

Fig. 13. Difference in severe values of the model with respect to the dataset.

Together, the present results of the extreme events analysis go beyond previous reports, showing that the Markov-Switching approach is capable of simulating extreme events. This is achieved by embedding a conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component within the SMSAR model. However, it is important to highlight the fact that the conditional component that has an additional effect on the simulation. Therefore, overestimated states from the MSAR model won't be improved by the SMSAR model. For example, the overestimated extreme event on 02/1915. Overall, superior results are seen for the SMASR model within the framework of extreme events detection.

3.3. Models Forecasting

To date, it remains unclear whether predicting directly the dataset or a simulation fitted to the dataset yields better results. In addition, the impact of the training period on pattern recognition has not been clearly investigated, which raises concerns about the precision of the predictions. Therefore, to test whether the previous statement is verifiable, the deep machine learning Neural Networks (NN) method [42] is considered for forecasting the dataset, the MSAR, and the SMSAR models. This method comprises the effect of monthly seasonality and the historical period length effect of 20 and 40 years on the period from 01/1931 to 12/1933. Subsequently, by comparing the predictions from the Neural Networks method of the dataset (Dataset NN), the SMSAR model (SMSAR NN), and the MSAR model (MSAR NN) with the available dataset of the mentioned period (Dataset), it is likely to investigate whether predicting the dataset or the alternatively based simulations provide better results.

In Fig. 14a, the observed Neural Networks predictions are based on a 20-year Historical Period Length, the results are compared with the realistic dataset of this period. Overall, the result indicates that the Dataset NN, the MSAR NN, and the SMSAR NN predictions can recognize the dataset patterns.

In Fig. 14b, the observed Neural Networks predictions are based on a 40-year Historical Period Length. Overall, the result indicates that the Dataset NN, the SMSAR NN, and the MSAR NN predictions can recognize the dataset patterns. In addition, predictions based on a 40-year Historical Period Length present a better fit than the predictions based on a 20-year Historical Period Length.

The results of the Neural Networks forecasts demonstrate that extending the training period within the Neural Networks prediction method enhances its capacity for accurately recognizing historical patterns.

Fig. 14. Neural Network simulation forecasts. (a) 20-year and, (b) 40-year Historical Period Length.

The precision of the predictions is presented in terms of descriptive values to determine the degree of accuracy and error. This provides an insight into which degree of inference whether predicting directly the dataset or alternatively a fitted simulation to the dataset is attributed to providing better results. Furthermore, it highlights the impact of the training period on pattern recognition.

In Table 2, the error indicators provide the accuracy of the Neural Networks simulations with respect to the dataset on the forecasted period from 01/1931 to 12/1933. The results of the simulations of the 40-year Historical Period Length yield better results than those of the 20-year Historical Period Length in terms of the degree of accuracy and error.

Table 2. Neural Network simulations error indicators.

Models	20-year Historical Period Length			40-year Historical Period Length		
	MAE*	RMSE**	R ^{2***}	MAE*	RMSE**	R ^{2***}
Dataset NN	35.6	45.4	0.42	30.0	36.8	0.52
SMSAR NN	38.2	46.1	0.48	22.5	27.2	0.71
MSAR NN	37.2	45.6	0.20	27.1	33.7	0.55

* Mean absolute error. (m³/sec)

** Square root of the average square errors. (m³/sec)

*** Coefficient of determination.

The results of the forecasting using the NN method indicate three key findings:

- The disproportion between the results of the fitted simulations, i.e., SMSAR NN and MSAR NN supports the notion that simulating a time series model requires access to experts who understand the relevant cause and effect of the dataset distribution, in which experts must be able to provide a recognizable pattern relevant to their priorities within the dataset. In this case, the proposed SMSAR model recognizes well the pattern and presents a significantly better fit than the MSAR model.
- Predicting a simulation fitted to the dataset is attributed to providing better results. In a sense, a simulation can integrate missing signals in the dataset and provide a recognizable pattern. This is indicated within the results of the SMSAR NN and MSAR NN compared to the Dataset NN.
- The training period impacts the accuracy of the forecasts. In this case, predictions of a 40-year Historical Period Length yield a better fit than those of a 20-year Historical Period Length,

since the length of the training process affects the ability of the Neural Networks to detect the patterns.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This paper proposes a stochastic Seasonal Markov-Switching Autoregressive (SMSAR) model to recognize the dynamic pattern of the river flow and to simulate the hydrological fact of rivers, i.e., high river flow values for a short time interval are followed by low river flow values for a long-time interval. In addition, it aims at improving the capacity of simulating river flow extreme events. This paper also investigates the precision of the predictions when considering the training period, i.e., Historical Period Length effect on the pattern recognition, and whether the predictive analysis of the dataset or equivalent simulations yields better results.

The main conclusions are summarized as follows:

- A better fit to the dataset is associated with the improvement embedded in the SMSAR model compared to the MSAR model. It is interesting to note that the SMSAR model seems to better present the shifting behavior of the time series with respect to the dataset. In addition, the distribution of the dataset in terms of shape and spread is better presented by the SMSAR model. The SMSAR model reaches the range limit value of the dataset. On the other hand, the MSAR model underestimated this value.
- The SMSAR model significantly improves the missing statistical information within the MSAR model for seasonal lags. In addition, the SMSAR model also improves the results for the non-seasonal lags.
- Within the framework of extreme events detection, the SMSAR model significantly improves the ability of the regime-switching technique to simulate extreme events. However, it is important to highlight the fact that the SMSAR model suffers from the fitting limitation associated with the MSAR model, in which the overestimation of the MSAR simulation cannot be adjusted.
- Within the framework of forecasting, predicting the SMSAR simulation yields better results than predicting the dataset directly. In a sense, a simulation can integrate missing signals in the dataset and provide a recognizable pattern. Furthermore, the training period, i.e., Historical Period Length impacts the accuracy of the predictions; this statement is evidenced by the

improvements adjusted by the NN simulations of the 40-year Historical Period Length when compared to the 20-year Historical Period Length.

- Future research should be devoted to the development of the proposed SMSAR model since the model underestimates some extreme events and shows some missing statistical information within the simulation. The authors suggest considering the yearly seasonal effect as a Hidden Seasonal Markov component within the model to increase the quality of the model. In addition, the proposed model can be adjusted to influence all the months.

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Appendix. 1. Pseudo-algorithm of the simulation methodology

```
BEGIN
READ Dataset

# Define the monthly time series
INPUT (Dataset, Start = Date, End = Date, Frequency =12)
OUTPUT Time series

# Stationary check:
COMPUTE KPSS test (Time series)
OUTPUT P-value && Statistic value
IF (P-value > p_Criteria && Statistic value < Intercept_Critical) THEN
    PRINT (Time series is stationary)
ELSE
    PRINT (Time series is non-stationary)
    SET Differencing order to zero
    CALCULATE Integration (Time series)
    OUTPUT Differencing order && Integrated Stationary Time series
END IF

# Choosing a model to fit the time series dataset:
COMPUTE Autocorrelation function (Time series)
OUTPUT Decay
IF (Decay = Slowly) THEN
    PRINT (Long-term models are required, i.e., MSAR or ARFIMA)
    COMPUTE Structural break test (Time series)
    OUTPUT P-value
    IF (P-value < 0.05) THEN
        PRINT (MSAR model is mandatory)
    ELSE
        PRINT (ARFIMA model is a preferable choice)
    END IF
ELSE
    PRINT (Short-term models are required, i.e., ARIMA)
END IF

# Simulate the MSAR model:
OBTAIN Array (Time series)
OUTPUT Time series array
INIT Akaike Info Criterion to zero
INIT j to 2
FOR i = 1 to 4
    COMPUTE MSAR (Time series array,  $\varphi[i]$ ,  $M[j]$ ) # Eq.(3)
    OUTPUT Fitted MSAR model
    COMPUTE Akaike info criterion
    STORE Fitted model && Akaike info criterion in Result [MSAR]
END FOR
READ the lowest value of Akaike info criterion in Result [MSAR][i]
OUTPUT Fitted MSAR model
```

```

# Calculate the hidden seasonal Markov component stating phase:
COMPUTE Months of interest increase rate ( $Moi_t$ ): # Eq. (5)
COMPUTE Months of interest effect value ( $Ev_t$ ): # Eq. (6)

# Calculate the hidden seasonal Markov component conditioning phase:
COMPUTE Yearly seasonality ( $S_y$ ): # Eq. (7)
COMPUTE Monthly effect value with respect to yearly seasonality ( $MES_y$ ): # Eq. (9)

# Calculate the Hidden Seasonal Markov component value:
COMPUTE Conditional Hidden Seasonal Markov component value ( $HSM$ ): # Eq. (10)

# Simulate the SMSAR model:
COMPUTE SMSAR (Fitted MSAR model, HSM): # Eq. (11)
OUTPUT SMSAR fitted model

# Extreme events:
CALCULATE  $E$  # Eq. (14): Severe values limit
SET n to length (Time series)
SET p to 1
WHILE p < n
    IF (Time series[p, 1], MSAR fitted model[p, 2] && SMSAR fitted model[p, 3]) >=  $E$ 
    THEN
        OUTPUT Extreme events values
        STORE Extreme events values in Result [Extreme events] [p, q]
    ELSE
        INCREMENT p
    END IF
END WHILE

# Neural Network forecasting
READ Time series, MSAR fitted model && SMSAR fitted model
STORE Time series, MSAR fitted model && SMSAR fitted model in Result [Simulations] [x, y]
SET y to 1
FOR x = 1 to n
    Neural network (Simulations [x, y], non-seasonal lags = 11, seasonal lags= (1,12))
    OUTPUT NN fitted simulations
    STORE NN fitted simulations in Result [Neural Network] [x, y]
    INCREMENT y
END FOR
GENERATE Forecast ([Neural Network] [1: n, 1: 3], periods of forecasting = 36)
    OUTPUT Forecasted values
    STORE Forecasted values in Result [Forecasts] [1: 36, 1: 3]

```